

The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions

It decreased by 12.90% between 2005 and 2020

The Istat-Bes calculates the "smoking" variable defined as a standardized proportion of 14-year-old people and more than they declare that they currently smoke on the total of 14-year-old people and more.

1. Ranking of Italian regions for smoking value in 2020

Emilia-Romagna is in the first place for the value of the percentage of smokers in the population over 14 with a value of 20.5, followed by Tuscany and Umbria with a value of 20.4 and Sicily with a value equal to 20.3. In the middle of the standings there are Marche and Lazio with a value of 18.7, Liguria with a value of 18.4 and Trentino-Alto Adige with a value of 18. They close the Veneto ranking with a value of 16.5, Puglia, with a value of 16.4 and Friuli-Venezia Giulia with an amount of 15.7.

2. Ranking of the Italian Regions by absolute variation of the percentage of smokers between 2005 and 2020

Basilicata is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of smokers with a value of 0.52% equal to an amount of 0.10 units, followed by the Trentino -Alto Adige with a variation equal to an amount of -3.74 % of a variation of -0.70 units and from Molise with a variation equal to an amount of -4.46% equal to a value of -0.90 units. In the middle of the standings there are the brands with a value equal to -8.33% equal to a variation of -1.70 units, followed by the Aosta Valley with a variation equal to an amount of -8.99% equal to a amount of 1.70 units and from Tuscany with a variation equal to a value of -9.33% equal to an amount of -2.10 units. Lazio close the ranking with a value of 21.76% equal to an amount of -5.20 units, Abruzzo with a value equal to -23.50% equal to an amount of -5.50 units and the Campania with a variation equal to a value of -23.58% equal to an amount of -5.80 units.

3. Italian macro-regions between 2005 and 2020

Looking at Italian macro-regions, it appears that the percentage of smokers in the population over the age of 14 has significantly decreased. In fact, in northern Italy in 2005 the percentage of smokers was equal to an amount of 21.30 and then decreased to 19.00% in 2020 or a variation equal to a value of -2.30 units equal to a variation of - 10.80%. In Central Italy, the percentage of smokers decreased from an amount of 23.00% up to a value of 19.20% or a variation of -3.80 units equal to a value of - 16.52%. In the South, the percentage of smokers decreased from an amount of 21.40% up to a value of 18.40% or equal to a variation of -3.00 units equal to a variation of -14.02%. Overall, in Italy the percentage of smokers decreased from an amount of 21.70% up to a value of 18.90% equal to a variation of -2.80 units equal to an amount of -12.90%.

4. K-means algorithm clusterization optimized through the silhouette coefficient

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Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized using the silhouette coefficient. The following Clusters were then identified:

- Cluster 1: Tuscany, Campania, Umbria, Sicily, Lazio, Piedmont, Liguria, Lombardy, Emilia-Romagna, Abruzzo, Marche, Basilicata;
- Cluster 2: Trentino-Alto Adige, Veneto, Calabria, Puglia, Valle d'Aosta, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Sardinia, Molise.

The median value of the percentage of smokers is calculated below in the interior of the individual Clusters or $C1 = 19.55$ units and $C2 = 17.1$. It therefore follows that $C1 > C2$. From a geographical point of view, a clear distinction between North, Center and South is not found in the distribution of smokers in the Clusters regions.

5. Network Analysis using Manhattan distance

A Network Analysis is presented below using Manhattan's distance. The data show the presence of some network structures of which one is complex or consisting of several nodes greater than 2 and the other two are simplified or consisting of 2 knots. The complex structure brings together the following regions in a network: Sicily, Abruzzo, Lombardy, Marche, Piedmont. Specifically there are the following reports:

- Sicily is connected to Lombardy with a link having a value of 1.7;
- Abruzzo is connected to Lombardy with a link having a value of 1.5 units;
- Lombardy is connected to the Marche with a link having a value of 1.6.
- The brands are connected to Piedmont with a link having a value of 1.7 units.

The two simplified network structures consist of the following links or:

- Veneto is connected to Calabria with a link having a value of 1.5 and vice versa.
- Trentino-Alto Adige is connected to Puglia with a link having a value of 1.6 and vice versa.

6. Conclusions

In summary, it is possible to underline that the percentage of smokers has significantly decreased in all Italian macro-regions and in all Italian regions except for Basilicata, between 2005 and 2020. Cluster analysis still shows a geographical trend that does not propose the classic distinction between regions of northern Italy, central Italy, and southern Italy by percentage of smokers. The significant reduction in the number of smokers in the Italian regions is certainly the consequence of the variation of individual behaviors that has been induced both by the change of the culture of status consumption and by the set of regulatory devices that have prevented smoking in many public places e Many means of transport. Certainly, an appropriate choice that has allowed not only to improve the health of Italians, but also to significantly lighten the health expenditure connected to the population of smokers.

7. Declarations

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9. Statistical Appendix

	2005	2020	Var Ass	Var Per
Nord	21,30	19,00	-2,30	-10,80
Centro	23,00	19,20	-3,80	-16,52
Mezzogiorno	21,40	18,40	-3,00	-14,02
Italia	21,70	18,90	-2,80	-12,90

Regioni	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Abruzzo	23,4	20,5	20,7	23,4	21,9	21,6	24	23,1	21,4	20,8	20,8	19,6	20,1	19,7	17,2	17,9
Basilicata	19,3	22	22,9	23,1	23	21,4	23,2	21,5	18,8	18,8	18,3	22	20,2	19,4	18,7	19,4
Calabria	19	19	16,6	20,5	20	20,6	18,8	19	18	16	17,6	15,8	16,4	16,3	15,5	17
Campania	24,6	25,9	25,4	23,1	22,3	25,6	22,6	23,8	22,5	21,9	22	23,1	20,8	18,7	19,3	18,8
Emilia-Romagna	22,1	24,2	21,7	23,4	24,5	22,6	21,2	20,7	21,3	19,9	21,1	20,4	19,8	17,7	18,4	20,5
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	17	21,5	20,9	21,3	20,8	21,9	21,8	21,6	19,3	20,4	18,9	19,6	18	16,6	18,1	15,7
Lazio	23,9	25,2	23,6	23,1	24,1	26,5	27,4	22,9	23,6	21,2	21,2	21,2	19,2	23,9	22,8	18,7
Liguria	21,6	20,3	24	21,6	23,6	21,4	21,9	22,2	20,6	18,9	23,3	22,5	23,2	20	19,8	18,4
Lombardia	22,9	21,9	21,2	22	23,2	22,4	22,7	22,4	20,4	19,7	19,3	20,6	20,8	19,3	17,5	19,8
Marche	20,4	21,2	22,8	21,6	23,4	23,3	21,8	20,7	19,3	20,3	19,7	19,5	20,8	21	17,2	18,7
Molise	20,2	19,3	20,9	20,6	20,8	21,3	21,9	21,7	19,2	18	21,9	20,6	20,6	17,3	20,3	19,3
Piemonte	20,8	22,1	22,3	21,4	23,2	22,4	23,2	21,3	20,9	20,7	20,6	20,6	21,7	21	20,7	19,7
Puglia	18,4	19,3	20,7	21,8	20,2	21,6	20,7	19,1	18,5	18,3	17,1	17,6	18,2	17,6	17,4	16,4
Sardegna	21	20,6	20,9	20,4	22,8	21	19,1	18,9	20,9	20	20,6	17,7	18,1	20	19,9	19,3
Sicilia	21,3	25	22,2	22,6	23,4	22,5	22,5	24,4	22	19,6	19,8	19,7	20,5	19,1	19,3	20,3
Toscana	22,5	23,1	23,1	22,9	24,7	23,1	23,4	24,5	23	17,8	20,9	21,1	21,3	21	20,6	20,4
Trentino-Alto Adige	18,7	18,9	20,1	20,4	19,1	19,7	18,1	19,3	17,7	18,3	16,8	17,2	16,9	18,1	15,9	18
Umbria	24,6	22,6	23,3	21,6	25	24	22,1	20,9	23,7	21,6	21,8	23,6	22,6	21	22,6	20,4
Valle d'Aosta	18,9	19,2	19,3	16,9	18,8	19,3	16	15,7	18,3	18,3	19	19,3	19,5	18,4	18,5	17,2
Veneto	19,2	19,3	18,7	20,3	22,1	20,3	18,5	19,9	18,7	16,6	17,5	16,6	18,1	17	15,8	16,5

Clusterizzazione C1>C2

Fumo nelle Regioni Italiane		
Rank	Regione	2020
1	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ 20,5
2	<i>Toscana</i>	★ 20,4
2	<i>Umbria</i>	★ 20,4
3	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ 20,3
4	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ 19,8
5	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ 19,7
6	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 19,4
7	<i>Molise</i>	★ 19,3
7	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ 19,3
8	<i>Campania</i>	★ 18,8
9	<i>Marche</i>	★ 18,7
9	<i>Lazio</i>	★ 18,7
10	<i>Liguria</i>	★ 18,4
11	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ 18
12	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ 17,9
13	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ 17,2
14	<i>Calabria</i>	★ 17
15	<i>Veneto</i>	★ 16,5
16	<i>Puglia</i>	★ 16,4
17	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ 15,7

**Variazione della percentuale dei fumatori tra il
2005 ed il 2020**

Rank	Regione	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Basilicata</i>	★ 0,10	★ 0,52
2	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	★ -0,70	★ -3,74
3	<i>Molise</i>	★ -0,90	★ -4,46
4	<i>Sicilia</i>	★ -1,00	★ -4,69
5	<i>Piemonte</i>	★ -1,10	★ -5,29
6	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	★ -1,60	★ -7,24
7	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	★ -1,30	★ -7,65
8	<i>Sardegna</i>	★ -1,70	★ -8,10
9	<i>Marche</i>	★ -1,70	★ -8,33
10	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	★ -1,70	★ -8,99
11	<i>Toscana</i>	★ -2,10	★ -9,33
12	<i>Calabria</i>	★ -2,00	★ -10,53
13	<i>Puglia</i>	★ -2,00	★ -10,87
14	<i>Lombardia</i>	★ -3,10	★ -13,54
15	<i>Veneto</i>	★ -2,70	★ -14,06
16	<i>Liguria</i>	★ -3,20	★ -14,81
17	<i>Umbria</i>	★ -4,20	★ -17,07
18	<i>Lazio</i>	★ -5,20	★ -21,76
19	<i>Abruzzo</i>	★ -5,50	★ -23,50
20	<i>Campania</i>	★ -5,80	★ -23,58

Variazione della percentuale dei fumatori tra il 2005 ed il 2020

